

SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITIONS OF A TYPICAL CANONICAL FORM.

(Amarnath Murthy ,S.E. (E &T), Well Logging Services, Oil And Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. ,Sabarmati, Ahmedbad, India- 380005.)

ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r) = F'(N)$,where

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

In the present note we derive a formula forr the case $N = p_1^\alpha p_2^2$

DISCUSSION:

Theorem(5.1):

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = F(\alpha, 2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} P(k) + \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-2j} \sum_{i=0} P(i)$$

where $r = [\alpha/2]$ $\alpha = 2r$ or $\alpha = 2r + 1$

PROOF: Following are the distinct mutually exclusive and exhaustive cases. Only the numbers in the bracket [] are to be further decomposed.

$$\text{Case I: } (p_2) [p_1^\alpha p_2^2] \text{ gives } F^*(p_1^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} P(i)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Case II: } \{A_1\} &\rightarrow (p_2^2) [p_1^\alpha] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha) \\ \{A_2\} &\rightarrow (p_2^2 p_1) [p_1^{\alpha-1}] \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-1) \\ &\vdots \\ \{A_\alpha\} &\rightarrow (p_2^2 p_1^\alpha) [p_1^{\alpha-\alpha}] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-\alpha) = P(0) \end{aligned}$$

Hence Case II contributes $\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha} P(i)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Case III: } \{B_1\} &\rightarrow (p_1 p_2) (p_1 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-2}] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-2) \\ \{B_2\} &\rightarrow (p_1 p_2) (p_1^2 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-3}] \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-3) \\ &\vdots \\ \{B_{\alpha-2}\} &\rightarrow (p_1 p_2) (p_1^{\alpha-1} p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-\alpha}] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-\alpha) = P(0) \end{aligned}$$

Hence Case III contributes $\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-2} P(i)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Case IV: } \{C_1\} &\rightarrow (p_1^2 p_2) (p_1^2 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-4}] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-4) \\ \{C_2\} &\rightarrow (p_1^2 p_2) (p_1^3 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-5}] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-5) \\ &\vdots \\ \{C_{\alpha-4}\} &\rightarrow (p_1^2 p_2) (p_1^{\alpha-2} p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-\alpha}] \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-\alpha) = P(0) \end{aligned}$$

Hence Case IV contributes $\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-4} P(i)$

{ **NOTE:** The factor partition $(p_1^2 p_2) (p_1 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-3}]$ has already been covered in case III hence is omitted in case IV. The same logic is extended to remaining (following) cases also. }

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Case V: } \{D_1\} &\rightarrow (p_1^3 p_2) (p_1^3 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-6}] && \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-4) \\ \{D_2\} &\rightarrow (p_1^3 p_2) (p_1^4 p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-7}] && \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-5) \\ &\vdots \\ \{D_{\alpha-4}\} &\rightarrow (p_1^3 p_2) (p_1^{\alpha-3} p_2) [p_1^{\alpha-\alpha}] && \text{-----} \rightarrow P(\alpha-\alpha) = P(0) \end{aligned}$$

Hence Case V contributes $\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-6} P(i)$

On similar lines case VI contributes $\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-8} P(i)$

we get contributions upto $\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-2r} P(i)$

where $2r < \alpha < 2r + 1$ or $r = [\alpha/2]$

summing up all the cases we get

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = F(\alpha, 2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} P(k) + \sum_{j=0}^r \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-2j} P(i)$$

where $r = [\alpha/2]$ $\alpha = 2r$ or $\alpha = 2r + 1$

This completes the proof of theorem (5.1).

COROLLARY:(5.1)

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = \sum_{k=0}^r (k+2) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)] \quad \text{-----(5.1)}$$

Proof: In theorem (5.1) consider the case $\alpha = 2r$, we have

$$F'(p_1^{2r} p_2^2) = F(\alpha, 2) = \sum_{k=0}^{2r} P(k) + \sum_{j=0}^r \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha-2j} P(i) \quad \text{-----(5.2)}$$

Second term on the RHS can be expanded as follows

$$\begin{aligned} &P(\alpha) + P(\alpha-1) + P(\alpha-2) + P(\alpha-3) + \dots + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\ &\qquad P(\alpha-2) + P(\alpha-3) + \dots + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\ &\qquad \cdot \qquad P(\alpha-4) + \dots + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\ &\qquad \cdot \\ &\qquad \cdot \\ &\qquad \qquad \qquad P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\ &\qquad \qquad \qquad \qquad P(0) \end{aligned}$$

summing up column wise

$$\begin{aligned} &= [P(\alpha) + P(\alpha-1)] + 2 [P(\alpha-2) + P(\alpha-3)] + 3 [P(\alpha-4) + P(\alpha-5)] + \dots \\ &\qquad + (r-1) [P(2) + P(1)] + r P(0). \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^r (k+1) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)]$$

{Here $P(-1) = 0$ has been defined.}

hence

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = \sum_{k=0}^r P(k) + \sum_{k=0}^r (k+1) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)]$$

or

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = \sum_{k=0}^r (k+2) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)]$$

Consider the case $\alpha = 2r+1$, the second term in the expression (5.2)

can be expanded as

$$\begin{array}{r}
P(\alpha) + P(\alpha-1) + P(\alpha-2) + P(\alpha-3) + \dots + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\
 P(\alpha-2) + P(\alpha-3) + \dots + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\
 P(\alpha-4) + \dots + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\
 P(3) + P(2) + P(1) + P(0) \\
 P(1) + P(0)
\end{array}$$

summing up column wise we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&= [P(\alpha) + P(\alpha-1)] + 2 [P(\alpha-2) + P(\alpha-3)] + 3 [P(\alpha-4) + P(\alpha-5)] + \dots \\
&\quad + (r-1) [P(3) + P(2)] + r [P(1) + P(0)]. \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^r (k+1) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)], \quad \alpha = 2r+1
\end{aligned}$$

on adding the first term , we get

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = \sum_{k=0}^r (k+2) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)]$$

{**Note** here P(-1) shall not appear.}
Hence for all values of α we have

$$F'(p_1^\alpha p_2^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{[\alpha/2]} (k+2) [P(\alpha-2k) + P(\alpha-2k-1)]$$

This completes the proof of the Corollary (5.1).

REFERENCES:

- [1] "Amarnath Murthy" , 'Generalization Of Partition Function, Introducing 'Smarandache Factor Partition', SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3, 2000.
- [2] " The Florentine Smarandache " Special Collection, Archives of American Mathematics, Centre for American History, University of Texax at Austin, USA.
- [3] 'Smarandache Notion Journal' Vol. 10 ,No. 1-2-3, Spring 1999. Number Theory Association of the UNIVERSITY OF CRAIOVA.